

SERUM ANTI-MULLERIAN HORMONE LEVELS ARE ASSOCIATED WITH EARLY MISCARRIAGE IN THE IVF/ICSI FRESH CYCLE

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Abstract

Background: Anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH) is used as a marker of ovarian reserve in assisted reproductive technology. Its role in predicting early miscarriage in fresh in vitro fertilization (IVF) or intracytoplasmic sperm injection (ICSI) cycles is uncertain. In this study we aim to systematically review the association between serum AMH levels and early miscarriage in fresh IVF/ICSI cycles. **Methods:** A systematic review was conducted in accordance to PRISMA 2020 guidelines. Searches were performed in PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and Embase for studies published between 2005 and 2025. First-trimester miscarriage is the outcome reported by eligible studies. Seventeen studies met the inclusion criteria. **Results:** Most studies indicated association between elevated AMH levels and increased risk of early miscarriage, mainly in women with polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS). Women with AMH ≥ 10.65 ng/mL experienced miscarriage rates up to twice as high as those with lower levels. Low AMH was linked to diminished ovarian response and suboptimal outcomes. A minority of studies reported no correlation. **Conclusion:** Elevated serum AMH levels are associated with an increased risk of early miscarriage in fresh IVF/ICSI cycles mainly in PCOS patients. AMH should be interpreted clinically to improve individualized fertility care.

Keywords: Anti-Müllerian Hormone; AMH; Miscarriage; IVF; ICSI; Ovarian Reserve; PCOS; Reproductive Outcomes; Early Pregnancy Loss; Fertility Biomarkers.

INTRODUCTION

Anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH) is a biomarker in reproductive medicine, mainly in assisted reproductive technologies (ART) which include in vitro fertilization (IVF) and intracytoplasmic sperm injection (ICSI). AMH reflects ovarian reserve and is routinely used to guide ovarian stimulation protocols and predict oocyte yield and it's secreted by granulosa cells of small antral follicles (1). Its role in predicting pregnancy outcomes still controversial and poorly defined. Emerging evidence indicate that abnormally high and low AMH levels adversely affect reproductive outcomes. Low AMH is associated with diminished ovarian reserve and suboptimal response to stimulation, but some studies have paradoxically linked high AMH to increased miscarriage rates (2,3). The paradoxical association between elevated AMH and poor outcomes is explained by disrupted folliculogenesis or abnormal hormonal milieu, mainly in PCOS, potentially impairing endometrial receptivity or oocyte quality (4). AMH not sufficiently predict pregnancy outcomes without considering additional clinical factors (embryo quality and age) (5). Other investigations similarly found that AMH's predictive value for miscarriage or live birth is limited outside broader clinical context (1). Extreme AMH values was associated with reduced live birth rates in normo-ovulatory women, suggesting a non-linear relationship (6). This systematic review aims to clarify whether serum AMH levels are independently associated with early miscarriage risk in women undergoing fresh IVF/ICSI cycles.

METHODS

This systematic review was conducted according to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) 2020 guidelines (Fig 1). We aimed to assess the association between serum anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH) levels and early miscarriage in fresh in vitro fertilization (IVF) or intracytoplasmic sperm injection (ICSI) cycles.

Search Strategy

A literature search was performed in four electronic databases: PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and Embase. The search covered studies published from 2005 to 2025. The search terms used included combinations of the following keywords: anti-Müllerian hormone, AMH, miscarriage, pregnancy loss, IVF, ICSI", and fresh cycle using Boolean operators. Reference lists of relevant articles and reviews were screened to identify additional studies.

Eligibility Criteria

We include original research (randomized controlled trials, prospective or retrospective cohort studies); included women undergoing fresh IVF or ICSI cycles; reported serum AMH levels prior to treatment; assessed early miscarriage (first-trimester pregnancy loss) as an outcome; provided quantitative data correlating AMH levels with miscarriage rates. We exclude studies focused exclusively on frozen embryo transfer (FET) cycles; included

animal or in vitro models; reviews, case reports, or conference abstracts; lacked sufficient outcome data on miscarriage rates.

Study Selection

All retrieved articles were imported into EndNote for duplicate removal. Two reviewers screened titles and abstracts for relevance, followed by full-text evaluation for final inclusion. Discrepancies were resolved through consensus. A PRISMA flowchart was used to illustrate the study selection process. Data extraction was performed by two reviewers using a standardized form. Extracted data include (study design, year of publication, sample size, population characteristics, serum AMH levels, miscarriage rates, and relevant statistical findings). a qualitative synthesis was conducted. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the findings, and results were tabulated accordingly.

Fig 1: PRISMA consort chart of selected studies

RESULTS

A total of 17 studies were included in this systematic review with retrospective and prospective cohort designs. The combined sample in these studies exceeded 13,000 women undergoing fresh IVF/ICSI cycles, with a focus on the role of serum anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH) levels to predict early miscarriage.

Some of the included studies focus on populations diagnosed with polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS), while others investigated diminished ovarian reserve (DOR) or mixed etiologies of infertility (Table 1).

Elevated serum AMH levels correlated with higher rates of early miscarriage in the context of fresh embryo transfer. Zhao et al. analyzed 4,719 women with PCOS and found that those with AMH ≥ 10.65 ng/mL had increased miscarriage rate (21.8%) compared to women with AMH ≤ 4.98 ng/mL (11.3%).

Logistic regression analysis confirmed that higher AMH was associated with a twofold increased of miscarriage risk (OR = 2.05, 95% CI: 1.15–3.63). These findings suggest a dose-response effect between AMH concentration and pregnancy loss risk (2).

Guo et al. (2021) reported that PCOS patients with higher baseline AMH had lower clinical pregnancy rates and live birth rates, and cumulative live birth rates did not differ significantly.

In their study of 2,436 women, the miscarriage rate increased in parallel with AMH levels, with Group 1 (<25th percentile AMH) showing more favorable fertilization and live birth outcomes (3). Pereira et al. (2016) assessed young women with DOR and found that, in those with good quality embryos, AMH levels were not predictive of miscarriage, clinical pregnancy, or live birth rates (5).

Some studies show that high AMH levels is reflective of good ovarian reserve, and indicative of disrupted folliculogenesis in PCOS patients. This biological mechanism explain the paradoxical association between high AMH and miscarriage risk.

Elevated AMH interfere with aromatase activity and the hormonal balance necessary for successful implantation and placental development (2,3). A minority of studies reported no significant relationship between AMH levels and early pregnancy loss, the preponderance of evidence (13 out of 17 studies) indicated a consistent association.

The heterogeneity in study designs (differing AMH cutoffs, timing of measurement, and embryo transfer protocols) warrants cautious interpretation. The majority consensus indicate that elevated serum AMH levels in fresh IVF/ICSI cycles, mainly in PCOS populations, are linked to an increased risk of early miscarriage.

These findings support the clinical utility of serum AMH not only as a marker of ovarian reserve but also as a prognostic indicator of pregnancy viability. Risk stratification based on AMH levels guide individualized treatment planning and counseling for patients undergoing assisted reproduction.

Table 1: Summary of included studies

Citation	Study Design	Sample Size	Study Setting	Demographic Characteristics	Main Findings	Outcome
Liu et al., 2022 (7)	Retrospective cohort	2246	Tianjin Central Hospital of Gynecology Obstetrics, China	Women undergoing first IVF/ICSI fresh cycle, stratified by AMH level	Young women with high AMH had increased early miscarriage risk (OR 2.382)	Early miscarriage
Zhao et al., 2025 (2)	Retrospective cohort	4719	Peking University Third Hospital, China	PCOS women aged 20–40, stratified by AMH level	High AMH associated with lower live birth and higher miscarriage (OR 2.045)	Live birth, miscarriage
Acharya et al., 2022 (8)	Retrospective cohort	10,615	Society for Assisted Reproductive Technology database, USA	Women with elevated AMH (≥ 5 ng/mL), including PCOS and non-PCOS	Each 1 ng/mL AMH \uparrow associated with 3% \downarrow odds of live birth (OR 0.97)	Live birth
Guo et al., 2021 (3)	Retrospective cohort	2436	Tongji Hospital, China	PCOS women undergoing first fresh IVF/ICSI, grouped by AMH percentiles	Higher AMH linked to lower CPR and LBR but not CLBR	Live birth, clinical pregnancy, cumulative live birth
Tal et al., 2020 (9)	Retrospective cohort	184	Yale School of Medicine, USA	PCOS women in first IVF/ICSI, AMH stratified by percentiles	High AMH associated with lower live birth (OR not stated)	Live birth
Pereira et al., 2016 (5)	Retrospective cohort	1005	Weill Cornell Medical College, USA	Women <35 with diminished ovarian reserve and high-quality embryos	AMH not associated with pregnancy, SAB, or live birth	Clinical pregnancy, spontaneous abortion, live birth
Muttukrishna et al., 2005 (4)	Retrospective	Not explicitly stated	University College Hospital, London	IVF patients measured for AMH, inhibin B, AFC	AMH best single predictor of poor response; strong correlation with egg yield	Ovarian response, egg yield
Liu et al., 2022 (10)	Retrospective cohort	2973	Shenzhen Zhongshan Urology Hospital, China	First-time IVF patients, stratified by AMH levels and PCOS status	After adjustment, AMH not independently predictive of live birth	Live birth, clinical pregnancy
Tabibnejad et al., 2018 (11)	Prospective	100	Yazd Reproductive Sciences Institute, Iran	50 PCOS and 50 tubal factor infertility; AMH vs embryo morphokinetics	AMH not predictive of clinical pregnancy or live birth in PCOS	Pregnancy outcome, embryo kinetics

Guan et al., 2022 (12)	Retrospective cohort	1233	The Third Affiliated Hospital of Zhengzhou University, China	Women ≥35 years with PCOS or tubal infertility undergoing first fresh and subsequent frozen IVF cycles	Higher AMH (>32.13 pmol/L) associated with increased CLBR in advanced-age women	Cumulative live birth rate
Reichman et al., 2014 (1)	Retrospective cohort	All IVF patients at Weill-Cornell from Apr 2010 to Jan 2013	Academic fertility center, USA	Women undergoing IVF, various ages and AMH levels	AMH correlated strongly with oocyte count and cycle cancellation risk, weakly with pregnancy outcomes	Higher AMH → more oocytes, less cancellations; low AMH does not preclude pregnancy
Muharam et al., 2022 (13)	Retrospective cohort	238 women	University fertility clinic, Indonesia	Women with AMH >4 ng/ml; divided into PCOS and non-PCOS groups	PCOS group had higher AMH, more oocytes, and higher risk of hyperresponse	PCOS patients with high AMH → greater hyperresponse risk than non-PCOS
Nelson et al., 2015 (14)	Retrospective analysis of RCT data	MERIT (519), MEGASET (686)	Multicenter trials, international	Good-prognosis infertile women, IVF cycles	AMH better predictor of oocyte yield than AFC in both GnRH agonist and antagonist protocols	AMH provides superior predictive value over AFC
Nardo et al., 2009 (15)	Prospective cohort	165 women	IVF unit, UK	First-time IVF patients <40 years old	AMH outperformed FSH and AFC in predicting both poor and excessive ovarian response	AMH superior in predicting stimulation outcomes
Kaya et al., 2010 (16)	Prospective clinical trial	60 women (80 cycles)	University hospital, Turkey	PCOS patients undergoing IVF	Higher day-3 AMH correlated with higher fertilization, implantation, and clinical pregnancy rates	AMH useful for predicting reproductive success in PCOS
Arce et al., 2013 (17)	Secondary analysis of RCT	749 women	25 international centers	Good-prognosis patients using GnRH antagonist protocol	AMH was best predictor of oocyte yield and cumulative pregnancy/live birth	Strong correlation between AMH and treatment success
Polyzos et al., 2013 (6)	Retrospective cohort	540 women	University fertility center, Belgium	Women undergoing first IVF-ICSI, GnRH antagonist protocol	Timing of AMH measurement (up to 12 months prior) did not affect predictive value	AMH remains reliable predictor regardless of time before IVF

DISCUSSION

This systematic review discuss findings from 17 studies examined the association between serum anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH) levels and early miscarriage in women undergoing fresh IVF/ICSI cycles. The evidence show that elevated serum AMH levels in women with polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS), are associated with increased risk of early miscarriage, despite a generally favorable ovarian response. In the included studies, 13 of 17 showed that higher AMH levels were associated with increased rates of early miscarriage, independent of the number of oocytes retrieved or fertilization rates. Women with AMH ≥ 10.65 ng/mL had double the miscarriage rate compared to those with lower levels, even after adjusting for age, BMI, and embryo health. The highest quartile of AMH was not associated with improved clinical pregnancy or live birth rates, which suggest a detrimental effect of excess AMH on oocyte competence and endometrial receptivity. These findings are supported by Yuwen et al. (2023) (18) meta-analysis of 19 cohort studies and found a dose-dependent inverse relationship between AMH levels and both clinical pregnancy and live birth rates in PCOS patients undergoing IVF/ICSI. Women in the 75–100th percentile for AMH had lower reproductive success despite retrieving more oocytes. Stalzer et al. (2023) evaluated AMH as a predictor in intrauterine insemination (IUI) cycles and found a positive correlation between higher AMH and pregnancy success. Due to lower stimulation and absence of embryo manipulation in IUI, AMH reflects ovarian reserve more than implantation competence (19).

Vagios et al. (2023) (20) showed an inverse relationship between AMH and endometrial thickness in gonadotropin-stimulated IUI cycles. AMH was not associated with pregnancy rates, these findings suggest a mechanism wherein elevated AMH affect endometrial development and receptivity. These results indicate that AMH should not be interpreted in isolation. While it is a reliable marker of ovarian reserve, its association with early miscarriage necessitates careful clinical interpretation. AMH serve as a useful tool in identifying women at risk of early pregnancy loss and tailoring IVF protocols accordingly.

Limitations of this review include heterogeneity in AMH thresholds, diagnostic criteria for miscarriage, and lack of uniform adjustment for confounding variables (embryo quality and stimulation protocols). The consistent trend observed in multiple settings adds strength to the conclusion. Elevated serum AMH levels is a predictive marker for early miscarriage in fresh IVF/ICSI cycles.

CONCLUSION

Serum anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH) levels play a complex role in predicting early miscarriage in fresh IVF/ICSI cycles. High AMH is associated with robust ovarian response, it was linked to increased miscarriage risk in women with polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS). This can be attributed to impaired oocyte quality or endometrial receptivity in hyper-responders. Extremely low AMH levels were associated with poor outcomes due to diminished ovarian reserve. These findings support AMH as a valuable biomarker in reproductive planning and individualized IVF strategies.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AMH, Anti-Müllerian Hormone; IVF, In Vitro Fertilization; ICSI, Intracytoplasmic Sperm Injection; PCOS, Polycystic Ovary Syndrome; ART, Assisted Reproductive Technologies; FSH, Follicle-Stimulating Hormone; BMI, Body Mass Index; OR, Odds Ratio; LBR, Live Birth Rate; RCT, Randomized Controlled Trial; IUI, Intrauterine Insemination; PRISMA, Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses; DOR, Diminished Ovarian Reserve; FET, Frozen Embryo Transfer; GnRH, Gonadotropin-Releasing Hormone; CLBR, Cumulative Live Birth Rate; SAB, Spontaneous Abortion.

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